

A CASE REPORT: EFFECT OF VAMANA KARMA (SHODHANA CHIKITSA) AND SHAMANA CHIKITSA IN KITIBHA KUSHTHA

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ABSTRACT

Skin diseases can significantly affect psychological and social well-being, often leading to depression, social isolation, loneliness, and a reduced quality of life. The World Health Organization recognizes many skin conditions as psychocutaneous disorders, highlighting the close connection between the skin and the mind. As a result, patients tend to give high importance to the treatment of skin ailments. These conditions are increasingly common due to lifestyle changes such as unhealthy dietary habits, stress, irregular sleep patterns, and poor hygiene. In *Ayurveda*, most skin diseases are categorized under *Kushtha Roga*. **Aim:** To evaluate the effect of *Vamana Karma (Shodhana Chikitsa)* and *Shamana Chikitsa* in the management of *Kitibha Kushtha*. **Material And Methods:** A male patient aged 37 years presented with the signs and symptoms of *Shyava Varna* (blackish-brown discoloration), *Kina Khara Sparsha* (rough texture), *Parushata* (dryness), *Ruksha Pidika* (eruptions), and *Kandu* (itching) diagnosed it as *Kitibha Kushtha*, was treated with *Vamana Karma* (emesis) followed by prior *Pachana Karma* and *Bahya & Abhyantara Snehana* (external & internal oiling) followed by *Swedana* (fomentation). After *Shodhana* Patient was treated with *Shamana Chikitsa* for 15 days. PASI Score and gradations were applied for the assessment of all symptoms. **Observation And Result:** After the treatment PASI Score was reduced to 1.2 from 9.6. Significant results were observed and symptoms of *Kitibha Kushtha* were reduced. It also shows significant changes in gradations. photographic records were maintained for comparative evaluation. **Conclusion:** It can be concluded that *Vamana Karma (Shodhana Chikitsa)* along with *Shamana Chikitsa* is effective in the management of *Kitibha Kushtha*.

KEYWORDS: *Vamana Karma, Shoshana Chikitsa, Kitibha Kushtha.*

INTRODUCTION

Among the sense organs, the skin plays a vital role in protecting the body from external factors. It is the largest organ, readily visible for examination and highly susceptible to injury and disease. The condition of the skin, including complexion, is influenced by factors such as nutrition, hygiene, circulation, age, immunity, genetic predisposition, and mental state.

In *Ayurveda*, the body is described by the principle “*Dosha Dhatu Mala Mulam Hi Shareeram*”^[1] Any imbalance (*Dushti*) among these components can lead to

disease (*Vikara*). The skin is referred to as *Twak*, and all skin disorders (*Twak Vikara*) are broadly categorized under *Kushtha*.^[2] *Charaka* has included *Kushtha* among the *Ashtamahagada*, indicating conditions that are difficult to manage or cure.

The concept “*Kushnati Shareerasya Shonitam Vikrute*” implies that vitiation of *Rakta Dhatu* plays a key role in the development of *Kushtha*.^[3] The causative factors (*Nidana*) of skin disorders primarily includes excessive and improper intake of incompatible foods and habits such as contradictory use of hot and cold substances,

excessive consumption of heavy and saturating foods, use of inferior grains with milk, curd, buttermilk, oils, and pulses, mental stress, which lead to the vitiation of *Tridosha*. This, in turn, affects *Rasa*, *Rakta*, *Mamsa*, and *Lasika*, contributing to disease progression.^[4]

Kushtha is further classified into *Mahakushtha* (major disorders) and *Kshudra Kushtha* (minor disorders). The present condition can be correlated with *Kitibha Kushtha* due to its similar clinical features. According to *Charaka*, *Kitibha Kushtha* is a type of *Kshudra Kushtha* and is considered a *Raktapradoshaja Vikara* caused by the aggravation of *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas*. It presents with symptoms such as *Shyava Varna* (blackish-brown discoloration), *Kina Khara Sparsha* (rough texture), *Parushata* (dryness), *Ruksha Pidika* (eruptions), and *Kandu* (itching).^[5] The condition is understood to involve the vitiation of multiple bodily elements, including *Tridosha*, *Twak*, *Rakta*, *Mamsa*, and *Lasika*.

In Ayurveda, the management of *Kushtha* is planned based on factors such as *Bala* (patient strength), *Dosha* predominance, and the stage of the disease (*Vyadhi Avastha*). Accordingly, both *Shodhana* (purificatory therapy) and *Shamana* (palliative treatment) are advised. In conditions characterized by *Bahu Dosha Avastha*, *Shodhana* therapy is preferred to eliminate the aggravated *Doshas* and address the root cause of the disease. In this case, *Kitibha Kushtha* was effectively

managed with *Vamana Karma*, followed by *Shamana Aushadhi*.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the effect of *Vamana Karma* (*Shodhana Chikitsa*) and *Shamana Chikitsa* in the management of *Kitibha Kushtha* through a case study.

CASE DESCRIPTION

37 years old male with MR no. 664188 on 21st march 2026 visited *Panchakarma* OPD (OPD no. 06) Sane Guruji Aarogya Kendra, Hadapsar, Pune. Patient approached with complaints of *Shyava Varna* (blackish-brown discoloration), *Kina Khara Sparsha* (rough texture), *Parushata* (dryness), *Ruksha Pidika* (eruptions), and *Kandu* (itching) over both legs associated with severe itching, Mild appearance of symptoms on knees and elbows. He is suffering since 3 years and got bleeding from lesions while scrapping.

History of present illness: since he is suffering from 3 years, consulted homeopathic doctor and took treatment. For few days the lesions subsided but later it aggravates. So patient approached our hospital for treatment of the same.

Past history- No history of Thyroid disorder/DM/HTN

Family history- No Significant history.

Personal history: Table no. 1.

On examination	Ashtavidha Parikshan	Dashavidha Parikshan
P – 78/min	Nadi – Vatakaphaj	Dushya – Rasa, Rakta, Mansa
BP – 120/80 mm of Hg	Jivha- Ishat sama	Desha- Sadharana
CNS–conscious & oriented	Mala- Unsatisfied	Bala- Madhyama
CVS- S1 S2 normal	Mutra- samyaka	Kala – Aadana
RS- AEBE clear	Shabda – prakruta	Anala- Vishama
P/A soft, no tenderness	Sparsha- Aushnashita	Prakruti- Vatakaphaj
	Druka – Prakruta	Vaya – Madhyama
	Akruti- Madhyama	Satmya- Shadarasa
		Ahara- Mishra Ahara

Local Skin Examination

Inspection - Dark brownish black pigmentation raised above the skin Palpation - Warmth touch with rough texture

Sign: Candle Grease Sign Positive.

Laboratory Investigation for Vamana procedure

Hb- 13.8 gm%, ESR – 10mm/hr, BSL random – 92mg/dl

Urine routine was normal

ECG and chest x ray were normal

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Centre of Study: This study was carried out in *Panchakarma* Department of Sane Guruji Aarogya Kendra, Hadapsar, Pune.

Treatment

Shodhana Chikitsa (purification) and *Shamana Chikitsa*

(palliative) was given to the patient in the following sequence

- *Amapachana* (appetizer)
- *Snehapana* (oleation therapy)
- *Vamana* (Emesis)
- *Shamanoushadhi* (Internal medicine)
- *Pathya-Apathya* (Do's and Don'ts)

In *Shodhana Chikitsa*, patient was administered with *Vamana Karma* (emesis) in proper sequence of *Purvakarma*, *Pradhanakarma*, *Paschyatkarma*.

Purvakarma

1. *Aampachana* : Given for 5 days
Panchakola churna 2gm *Vyanodana* with *koshnajala*

2. *Abhyantara Snehapana* : *Sneha- Goghruta*

Samyaka Snehana Lakshana was achieved in 5 days as given below.

Table no. 2

Date	Day	Matra	Snehapana Samaya	Kshudhabodha	Jaranakala	Lakshanas
29/03/26	D1	30ml	7:30 am	2:30 pm	7 hrs	Hrullasa
30/03/26	D2	60ml	7:10 am	5:30 pm	10 hrs 20 mins	-
31/03/26	D3	90ml	6:45 am	6:15 pm	11 hrs 30 mins	Hrullasa, shirogurava, shithila malapravrutti
01/04/26	D4	120ml	7:00 am	6:45 pm	11 hrs 45 mins	Alpa sneha dwesha, alpatwak snigdha, Asamhata mala pravartana
02/04/26	D5	150ml	6:45 am	8:15 pm	13 hrs 30 mins	Snehadwesa, twak snigdha, adhadast snehadarshana, Asmhata Malapravrutti

1. *Bahya Sarvanga Snehana* And *Swedana* :
2. 2 days After completion of *Snehapana* (3/4/26 and 4/4/26)

Sarvanga Snehana: Tila Taila

Sarvanga Swedana: *Bashpa Peti Sweda*

Pradhanakarma

1. *Vamana*: 1 day after *Abhyanga* and *Swedana* at early morning (4/4/26)

Aakanthapana: *Godugdha*

Vamaka yoga: *Apamarga Kwatha* 80 ml + *Madanphala pippali* 3gms + *Madhu* 10ml + *Saindhava* 0.5gms

Vamanopaga: *Yashtimadhu Kwatha* & *Saindhavajala*.

Table no. 3.

Time	Consumed Dravya	Quantity	Vomited Dravya	Symptoms	Vitals
7:30 am	<i>Godugdha</i>	1 lt	-	-	P- 78/min BP-120/80 mm Hg
7:40 am	<i>Vamaka Yoga</i>	-	-	-	-
7:55 am	-	-	-	<i>Swdapavrutti</i>	-
8:05 am	-	-	-	<i>Udaragauravta,</i> <i>Udgaraprachiti</i>	-
8:10 am	-	-	-	<i>mukhaparseka</i>	-
8:15 am	<i>Yashtimadhu Kwatha</i>	2 glass (460ml)	-	<i>Swdadhikya, Hrullasa</i>	P- 84/min BP-120/80 mm Hg
8:20 aam	<i>Yashtimadhu kwatha</i>	1 glass (230ml)	1	<i>Sakapha, Sadugdha,</i> <i>Sakwatha Pravartana</i>	-
8:30 am	<i>Yashtimadhu Kwatha</i>	6glass(1380ml)	1	<i>Sadugdha sakwatha pravartana Aushadhi Pravartana</i>	P-88/min BP- 130/90 mm Hg
8:45 am	<i>Yashtimadhu Kwatha</i>	3glass (690ml)	1	<i>Kashay tikta asyata,</i> <i>Pittapravartana,</i> <i>shirashoola</i>	-
8:40 am	<i>Yashtimadhu Kwatha</i>	3glass (690ml)	1	<i>Kashayatikta asyata</i> ↓ <i>Shirashoola</i> ↓	P-100/min BP- 140/90 mm Hg
8: 45 am	<i>Saindhava Jala</i>	4glass (920ml)	1	<i>Sakwatha sasaindhavajala pravartana</i>	-
9:00 am	<i>Saindhava Jala</i>	6glass(1380ml)	1	<i>Shareera laghavata,</i> <i>Indreeya prasannata</i>	P-80/min BP-120/80 mm Hg

Evaluation of *Samyaka Vamana* as given below

Shuddhi Prakara - *Madhyama Shuddhi Antiki* -

Pittantaka

Vaigiki - 6 vega

Maniki - Input: 7050 ml & output: 7500 ml
Laingiki – sarvangalaghava, Prasannamana & indriya

with 2 Annakala was explained to the patient in the form of Peya, Vilepi, Yusha, Krut-akruta Yusha followed by normal diet.^[6]

Paschyatkarma

After Samyaka Vamana Lakshana, Virechanik Dhoompana was given for 5 minutes in each nostril with Vachadi Dhoom Varti. Samsarjana Krama for 5 days

Shamana chikitsa is given for 15 days after Samsarjana Krama and follow up is taken after 15 days.

Table no. 4

Medicine	Dose	Anupana	Route	Duration
Aarogyavardhini Vati	500mg twice a day after meal	Koshnajala	Oral	15 days
Gandhak Rasayana	250mg twice a day after meal	Koshnajala	Oral	15 days
Panchatiktaghrita	10ml twice a day after meal	Koshnajala	oral	15 days
Panchatiktaghrita	Once a day	-	External application	15 days

Table No. 5: Medicine and its Guna.

Medicine	Guna
Aarogyavardhini Vati ^[7]	Deepana, Pachana, Strotoshodhana, Hridya, Medonashak, Malashodhak, Kshudhavaradhak
Gandhaka Rasayana ^[8]	Rasa-raktadi Sapta Dhatushodhana, Balaviryavardhak, Paushtika, Agnideepak, Vatakapharoganashak, Kushthanashak, Kandunashak, Prajakarak
Panchatiktaghrita ^[9]	Kushthghna, Kandughna, Kledonashana

Pathya Apathya (Do's and Dont's)

- Pathya- Laghu Anna (light diet), Gritha Yukta Anna, Purana Dhanya, Mudga, Jangala Mamsa ras.
- Apathya- Ati Guru Anna (heavy diet), Amla Rasa, Dugdha, Dadhi (curd), Anupa Mamsa, Matsya, Tila, Guda (jaggery), Suppression of natural urges, day sleep,

night awakening, stress, excessive sun exposure.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Assessment was done with PASI Score and Gradations.

PASI Score

Table no. 6: Showing Grading- PASI.

Nature	Lesion score	Lower limbs
Erythema Itching Scaling	0-None 1-Slight	3
	2-Moderate 3-Severe	3
	4-Very Severe	2
Total lesion score(A)		8

Table no.7: Showing grading on the basis of area involved.

Area affected	Involved area %	grade	Lower Limbs
Area Score (B)	0%	0	3
	<10%	1	
	10-29%	2	
	30-49%	3	
	50-69%	4	
	70-89%	5	
	90-100%	6	

Table no. 8: Table showing assessment criteria.

Assessment criteria	Initial Visit (on lower limbs)	After Vamana (on lower limbs)
Erythema	3	1
Itching	3	1
Scaling	2	1
Total lesion score (A)	8	3
Area score (B)	3	1
Total A* B	24	3
Total body surface area	24 * 0.4	3 * 0.4
Total PASI score	9.6	1.2

Table no. 9: Showing evaluation of subjective parameters.

Sr. No.	Signs and symptoms	Before Vamana	After Vamana
1.	<i>Shyava Varna (Black brown discolouration)</i>	++	+
2.	<i>Kina Khara Sparsha (Rough texture)</i>	+++	+
3.	<i>Parusham (Dryness)</i>	++	+
4.	<i>Kandu (Itching)</i>	++	+

Where, Mild- +
Moderate- ++ Severe- +++

Table no. 10: Showing images of before and after treatment.

DISCUSSION**Samprapti in patient was as follows**

- Kitibha Kushtha is a Kaphavataja type of Kushtha; hence Vamana Karma is considered the best treatment for Kapha Dosha.
- According to Acharya Sushruta, Dosha Nirharana should be done in Dosha Vruddhi conditions, mainly through Vamana and Virechana.
- In Kushtha, all three Doshas are vitiated. Vamana Karma expels vitiated Kapha and Apakva Pitta, thereby relieving symptoms.^[10]
- As Aamashaya is the main seat of Kapha Dosha, Vamana Karma pacifies Kapha throughout the body by eliminating it from Aamashaya.
- Acharya Charaka described Kushtha as a Bahudoshaja Vyadhi, where Samshodhana therapy is essential.^[11]
- Acharya Vagbhata emphasized repeated Samshodhana in Kushtha Chikitsa through Vamana, Virechana, Raktamokshana, and Nasya.^[12]
- Vamana Karma removes vitiated Doshas and Kleda, leading to Strotoshodhana and enhancement of Dhatvagni, which helps in proper Dhatu formation.
- Gandhak Rasayan acts as Saptadhatu Shodhaka, Kushthaghna, Kandughna, and Vata-Kaphahara,

thereby reducing symptoms of Sidhma Kushtha.

- Aarogyavardhini Vati possesses Deepana, Pachana, Strotoshodhaka, and Kshudhavardhaka properties, helping in proper Rasa Dhatu formation.
- Panchatikta Ghrita acts as kushtaghna, kandughna, kledashoshana.

CONCLUSION

After completion of treatment, the PASI score was reduced from 9.6 to 1.2, along with marked improvement in the signs and symptoms of the patient. The results suggest that *Vamana Karma (Shodhana Chikitsa)* along with *Shamana Chikitsa* is effective in the management of *Kitibha Kushtha*. As *Kushtha* is a chronic and difficult-to-cure disease, prolonged treatment through both *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies is necessary to prevent recurrence.

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